

Analysis of the Sociotechnical factors and Their Impact on Social Debt

Table 1: Factor, Number of Studies, and Primary Studies

Factor	# Primary studies	Primary Studies
Communication	29	[PS1, PS7, PS8, PS9, PS11, PS15–PS21, PS24, PS28–PS39, PS42–PS45]
Collaboration and Social Structure	26	[PS1, PS7, PS8, PS9, PS11–PS19, PS24, PS28, PS30–PS38, PS39, PS43–PS45]
Coordination	27	[PS7, PS8, PS11, PS13–PS21, PS27, PS28, PS31–PS34, PS36–PS38, PS39, PS40, PS42–PS45]
Socio-technical Consistency	19	[PS1, PS7–PS9, PS12–PS16, PS19, PS28, PS31, PS33, PS34, PS37, PS38, PS39, PS43, PS45]
Cultural and Organizational Factors	26	[PS1, PS7–PS9, PS12–PS17, PS18–PS20, PS24, PS28, PS31–PS34, PS36–PS39, PS42–PS44]